

Diagnosics of PEMFC Degradation

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Results of AST of the EK single cell (50 cm²)

Accelerated Stress Test

pol. curves

EIS

CV

Accelerated stress test

- The AST test is devised according to DOE recommendations for electrocatalyst degradation
- The cell in a "driven" mode → voltage imposed via external device
- Nitrogen on the cathode, hydrogen on the anode (RH 100%)
- Cycling between 0.9 V and 0.6 VS (voltage ramps 1 V s^{-1})
- Cycle duration 40 s (10 s @ 0.6 V; 30 s @ 0.9 V)

Polarization Curves

Degradation

Polarization Change Curves

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Electrochemical active surface area

Calculated from intercept of the fitted polarization change curves

Resistance increase

Calculated from the slope of the fitted polarization change curves

Results from Cyclic Voltammetry tests during AST

Comparison between results obtained by CV and Polarization Change Curves Analysis

Number of cycles

CV – calculated from cyclic voltammetry experiments

PCA – calculated from Polarization change curves analysis

EIS degradation testing of EK single cell

Table 1. Measuring parameters for EIS measurements

Measuring parameter for EIS	Value
AC perturbation amplitude	10% of DC current
upper frequency limit	3981.1 Hz
lower frequency limit	0.01 Hz
duration of stabilization phase	5 min
duration of EIS measurement + DC point	30 min

Table 2. Operating parameters for EIS measurements

Operating parameter for EIS	Value
hydrogen flow stoichiometry on anode	2.0
air flow stoichiometry on cathode	4.0
inlet relative humidity of H ₂ at anode	83.4% RH (61 °C DPT)
inlet relative humidity of air at cathode	83.4% RH (61 °C DPT)
anode backpressure	0.5 bar(g)
cathode backpressure	0.5 bar(g)
current densities	0.3, 0.6, 1.2 A cm ⁻²
fuel cell temperature at inlet	65 °C

Measured EIS during AST 30 A (0.6 A/cm²)

Measured EIS @ BoL vs. 5000 Cy

Impedance model of a PEM fuel cell

Measured and simulated EIS during AST 30 A (0.6 A/cm²)

Extracted parameters from EIS during AST 30 A (0.6 A/cm^2)

LF intercepts during AST

LF intercepts at different current densities during AST

I. Pivac, I. J. Halvorsen, D. Bezmalinović, F. Barbir, F. Zenith: *Low-frequency EIS intercept as a diagnostic tool for PEM fuel cells degradation*, European Fuel Cell Technology & Applications Piero Lunghi Conference (EFC17), Naples, December 12-15, 2017 - submitted

Resistance change during AST

LFR – low frequency intercept from EIS

dV/di – slope of the polarization curve at EIS current

R – resistance from polarization curve fitting

RO – High frequency resistance from EIS

Key Findings and Conclusions

- The cell moderately degraded over 10000 cycles
- Significant recovery over weekends
- Polarization change curves analysis indicates slight loss of ECSA and slight increase in resistance
- Relatively good agreement (at least qualitatively) between
 - polarization change curves analysis and EIS measurements
 - polarization change curves analysis and CV measurements
- Low frequency intercept seems to be a good and easily measured indicator of degradation
- Better understanding of permanent/recoverable degradation and recovery mechanisms needed

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Thank you for your attention!

Hydrogen energy system on any scale!

1,4 kW wind turbine on the roof

1,6 kW PVs on the roof

Connected to the lab

H2 system in the Lab

Fuel cell stack 1,2 kW

Control unit

Electrolyzer (3 kW)

DC/DC converter

Electronic load 1,5 kW

Hydrogen storage

ATV Vehicle powered by fuel cell and hydrogen

Hydrogen is stored in metal hydrides bottles

Laboratory for new energy technologies

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- Fuel cell test station (1)
- System integration; components testing (4)
- Electrolyzer (single cell) test station (3)
- Segmented fuel cell (4)

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